

MISCONSTRUATION OF SPEECH ACT IN SELECTED NIGERIAN PRESIDENTIAL INAUGURAL SPEECHES

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ABSTRACT

This study presents a speech act analysis of the Inaugural speech of current Nigerian president and the immediate past president with the aim of identifying the discrepancies between the illocutionary act and perlocutionary force. The data for this study comprise two Presidential Inaugural Speeches, that of Muhammadu Buhari in 2015 and Current President Bola Ahmed Tinubu in 2023. The data was gotten from online media sources, and qualitatively analysed using Austin (1962) three dimensions of Speech Act: locution, Illocutionary act and perlocutionary act. Additionally, A survey that contains questions on public comprehension and interpretation on selected statement of both speeches was distributed to 200 people from different socio-background, as a pilot study for this research. The Study reveal that President Tinubu and Former President Buhari employed a variety of speech acts in their speeches, such as acknowledgment, declarations, promises, assurances, and appeals to unity. These speech acts were used for different reasons, including building trust, instilling optimism, highlighting policy goals, and fostering national cohesion. However, it was observed that the Pragmatic Force on some declarations met with misconstruation between speaker's intent and audience interpretation and perceptions. Based on these findings, the study recommends that political leaders and speechwriters should be cognisant of the power of speech acts and its pragmatic force on the public. Thus, political leaders should be meticulous, and state overtly their intent, in order to prevent misconstruation of illocutionary acts, which results into a wrong pragmatic force, which no doubt could significantly cause a miscarriage in leadership.

Keywords: Speech Acts, Illocutionary, Perlocutionary, Pragmatic Force

INTRODUCTION

Language is indeed an interesting phenomenon. It plays a crucial role in human existence. For instance, language serves as a means for communicating ideas and feelings to members of different social groups. This suggests that humans use language to achieve a lot of things. While they try to convey their feelings with meaningful linguistic utterances, they also consciously and cautiously use language to perform certain actions. As in the case of politics, Okoro (2017) submits that politicians through their speech use language rhetorically to their advantage to convince or persuade the public to carry out certain actions. This therefore implies that languages have the attribute of performing actions and thus create effect.

The term Speech Act is often associated with the theory of J. L. Austin (1962) and J. R. Searle (1969). The theory is basically concerned with the linguistic actions humans perform while speaking. According to Austin (1962), linguistic utterances do more than just to convey information; they can as well be equivalent to actions. For instance, the utterances; "I promise..." "I assure you..." as often found in the utterances of Nigerian political leaders, constitute appropriate actions of promising and to instill confidence respectively.

The effect of utterances on interlocutors is also the concern of Speech Act as Saeed (2006) describes the three facets, namely: locutionary act, illocutionary act and perlocutionary act. However, it is important to note that the illocutionary force of an utterance can be misconstrued, thus resulting in an unintended perlocutionary act. This is especially true in the discourse of Nigerian politics. In Nigeria political space, Presidential Inaugural Speech often serves as a significant ritual for any elected president. This is arguably the first formal linguistic responsibility he performs as an elected president. Thus, he makes use of language in a more intentional and cautious way, in order to persuade the citizens to express trust in his capabilities and his administration. The citizens on the other hand, read meanings in the presented speech in order to sufficiently comprehend the intentions of the incoming administration. Consequently, the interpretation of some of the statements contained in the speech of the president can often times be misconstrued, thus leading to discrepancies of

speaker's intent and audience perception or interpretation which eventually results in a misconstrued pragmatic force.

In line with the foregoing, this paper attempts to not just contribute to previous knowledge on Speech Act, but to bridge the gap that exist on speaker's intent and audience perception and interpretation within the context of Nigeria's politics. The aim of this study is to analyse aspects of the inaugural speech by former president, Muhammadu Buhari and current president, Bola Ahmed Tinubu with a view to identifying instances of Misconstruation by Nigerians. This study provides an answer to the following questions: what are the speech acts used in the inaugural speeches of Muhammadu Buhari and current president, Bola Ahmed Tinubu, what ways did the statements perform actions, what was the speaker's intent, and what was the perception of the citizens to the speech acts?

REVIEW OF RELATED WORKS

There are several studies conducted on Presidential Inaugural Speeches by different scholars. This is partly based on the fact that the office of the President is the highest political office in any democratic country. Thus, Speech presentations are part of the medium through which these political leaders connect with the citizens. Sameer (2017) carried out an analysis of speech act patterns of two Egyptian presidential inaugural speeches. Sameer's work is related to this study, in that the speeches were from different periods of two Egyptian presidents. However, he opines that the manner in which a person emerges president determines the content of his Inaugural address. He further submits that political leaders often use speech act in their speech to solicit support from their audience.

In another study, Ibrahim (2020) carried out a pragmatic analysis of the Inaugural speech of former president, Muhammadu Buhari. In his findings, he asserts that the speaker relied more on expressions that carries commisive acts. Olaniyi (2010) describes commisive acts as an act that commits the speaker to perform future actions. These may include acts such as promise, swearing, offering, and threatening as well as other similar acts.

Mbanusi and Ezeifeke (2023) examined implicatures found in the 2015 inaugural speech of Muhammadu Buhari. He submits that speech presenters should be conscious of the implicatures associated with their speeches to avoid negative implicature or interpretation. This work is relevant to the current study, as it foregrounds the potentiality of misconstruction in presidential inaugural speeches.

Osisanwo (2017) carried out a similar study on the Inaugural speech of Muhammadu Buhari. His study focuses on the pragmatics acts used in the speech, with emphasis on Buhari's controversial statement: "I belong to everybody and I belong to nobody." Osisanwo's research demonstrates that speech acts are driven by specific objectives. He supports this claim by conducting a thorough examination of the results obtained from his investigation. For instance, actions such as proposing, promising, stating, and assuring are utilized to communicate the speaker's intentions. Similarly, acknowledging, thanking, remarking, and saluting are employed to express recognition and gratitude. Furthermore, activities like appealing, reminding, instructing, advising, hoping, charging, informing, and extending serve as directives. Lastly, identifying, describing, and defining are utilized to provide detailed information on various topics. Furthermore, the practical actions were identified using various pragmatic techniques such as mutual understanding of the situation, importance, mentioning, and implication. In line with the aim of this study, Osisanwo's work is relevant, in that it provides instances of pragmatic acts in the inaugural speech of Muhammadu Buhari. Thus, laying a foundation for this study, by helping to outline aspects of the statement and actions performed by Muhammadu Buhari which was misconstrued.

On the inaugural speech of Bola Ahmed Tinubu, Lucas (2023) carried out a pragmatic analysis of President Tinubu's inaugural speech; he submits that the speech has a preponderance of assertive acts and commissive acts. This perhaps suggests that the President tries to assert his authority as the number one citizen of the country, and thereafter committing himself to a future cause of action relevant to his office. Anyanwu (2023) examined the speech act found in the presidential inaugural speech of President Tinubu, with the aim of exploring his communicative intentions and Illocutionary force. Using a qualitative method, Anyanwu (2023) reveals that the speech contains acts like

promising, assurances, pledges, acknowledgement, and appeals to unity. She submits that speech acts especially the ones found in speeches have the power to influence the public, shape their opinions as well as political discourse. Badmus et al. (2024) also observed a similar situation as he states that language in the context of political discourse is capable of revealing the ideologies of a speaker during a discourse. This work is relevant to the current study in that it shares similar scope which is emphasis on communicative intention, illocutionary acts and its subsequent perlocutionary force.

From the previous study reviewed, it is quite obvious that Presidential Inaugural Speeches enjoys the attention of researchers, using speech act theory. However, this study attempts to fill the gap found in the context of Presidential inaugural Speeches, which is the communicative intention and misconstruction found in the Illocutionary acts and Perlocutionary force of two Nigerian presidential inaugural speeches, using a descriptive qualitative approach.

THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK

Speech Act is a theory propounded by J.L. Austin and subsequently expanded by John Searle. The theory provides a framework for understanding how utterances perform actions in social contexts. Speech Act theory is pivotal in the study of pragmatics in that it focuses on aspects of language use that derives its interpretation from context, the intentionality and effects of utterances. According to Austin (1962), in his seminal work "How to Do Things with Words", he outlines vividly the performative nature of language. He believes that to say something outrightly implies doing something. Thus he classifies utterances into constatives and performatives. While the former may not necessarily denote actions in some context, the latter often does in any given social context. Thus, Austin strongly holds that language has the ability to perform actions, and argues that utterances not only describe or represent the world but also have the power to perform actions.

Austin highlights three dimensions of speech acts: locutionary, illocutionary, and perlocutionary acts. The locutionary act refers to the act of uttering words and producing meaningful sentences. For instance, saying "I promise to buy you a new car"

constitutes a locutionary act. The illocutionary act refers to the intended force or function of the utterance. It represents the speaker's communicative intention and the illocutionary force performed by the speech act. Using the same example, the illocutionary act of promising implies the speaker's commitment to fulfill the stated promise. The perlocutionary act on the other hand, refers to the intended effect or impact of the speech act on the hearer or audience. It encompasses the consequences or reactions that the speaker intends to elicit. In the case of the promise, the perlocutionary act might aim to inspire trust, reassurance, or a sense of obligation in the hearer.

John Searle, in his work "Speech Acts: An Essay in the Philosophy of Language" (1969), expand the ideas of Austin's dimensions of Speech Act. Consequently, Searle (1999) provides taxonomy of Speech acts by categorising them into the following: Assertives, Directives, Commissive, Expressives, and Declarations. Each of Searle's categories corresponds to one or more of Austin's three dimensions. For instance, an assertive speech act makes a statement of fact, directives seeks to influence or direct the behavior of the audience, commissives aims to commit the speaker to a future cause of action, expressives serve the function of familiarisation while declaratives aim to change the state of affairs (Yule, 1996). This study intends to draw upon the ideas of Austin contributions, using the three dimensions of Speech Act, however with emphasis on the Illocutionary Act and Perlocutionary force. This is with the aim of analysing aspects of misconstruction in communicative intentions and perlocutionary acts.

METHODOLOGY

The data for this study comprise two Presidential Inaugural Speeches, that of Muhammadu Buhari in 2015 and Current President Bola Ahmed Tinubu in 2023. Both speeches are available on media platforms. We extracted five aspects for each of the statements found in both speeches that were misconstrued by the public. The choice for analysing the speech of the past and the present is to identify similarities and differences of misconstruction found in both speeches. The data was gotten from online media sources, and thus subjected to speech act analysis, using Austin's three dimensions of Speech Act: locution, Illocutionary act and perlocutionary act (Austin,

1962). However, for this study emphasis is placed on the Illocutionary Act and Perlocutionary act in order to identify instances of misconstruction. A survey that contains questions on public comprehension and interpretation on selected statement of both speeches was distributed to 200 people from different socio-background, as a pilot study for this research. The analysis and findings are presented in a descriptive qualitative approach. However, the findings from the survey will be presented in percentage.

DATA PRESENTATION AND ANALYSIS

(Excerpt from Muhammadu Buhari Inaugural Speech)

Data 1.

Locution: *"Today marks a triumph for Nigeria and an occasion to celebrate her freedom and cherish her democracy. Nigerians have shown their commitment to democracy and are determined to entrench its culture. Our journey has not been easy but thanks to the determination of our people and strong support from friends abroad we have today a truly democratically elected government in place."*

Illocutionary Act: The first two sentences is an act of assertion, while the third sentence denotes an act of appreciation. However, the last sentence is suggestive of an assertive act that inspires inclusivity and hopefulness among the citizens in the struggle to maintain democracy.

Misconstruction: The last sentence suggests that prior to the 2015 elections; the governments of other presidents were undemocratic.

Perlocutionary Effect: This creates an effect of distrust and disillusionment in the electoral process of the country.

Data 2.

Locution: *"Having just a few minutes ago sworn on the Holy Book, I intend to keep my oath and serve as President to all Nigerians. I belong to everybody and I belong to nobody."*

Illocutionary Act: The first sentence performs the act of committing to a future course (Commissives). The last sentence, although vague, but it's not devoid of pragmatic underpinnings. This sentence performs the act of assertion, and Commissive. Here the former President resolved to treat Nigeria and Nigerians (though Multicultural) equally.

Misconstruation: This statement from the former president created confusion in the hearts of the citizens. 80% of the responses from the questionnaire believe the former president wanted to segregate between the Northern people who massively voted him into power and the southerners. However 20% thinks the former president asserted that he will be free from external political influence.

Perlocutionary Effect: This statement from the former President creates the effect of doubts and non-inclusivity.

Data 3.

Locution: *"A few people have privately voiced fears that on coming back to office I shall go after them. These fears are groundless. There will be no paying off old scores. The past is prologue."*

Illocutionary Act: This is an assertion is indicative of the act of promising. This suggests an act of assurance.

Misconstruation: 90% of responses from the survey suggest that the president meant the exact opposite of this statement. This is because most of the participants believe that he has a reputation of going after his socio-political antagonists.

Perlocutionary Effect: This creates an effect of insincerity and distrust.

Data 4.

Locution: *"As far as the constitution allows me I will try to ensure that there is responsible and accountable governance at all levels of government in the country. For I will not have kept my own trust with the Nigerian people if I allow others abuse theirs under my watch."*

Illocutionary Act: The act is commissive, and indicates the interest of the former president to make all tiers of government accountable and responsible. This creates an inspiration of hope for a more responsible and committed government, and a sense of respect for the rule of law.

Misconstruation: This assertion by the president expects to inspire confidence and hope, however the attitude of most of Nigerians is "Let's Watch and See".

Perlocutionary Act: This creates a sense of uncertainty.

Data 5.

Locution: *"Boko Haram is a typical example of small fires causing large fires. An eccentric and unorthodox preacher with a tiny following was given posthumous fame and following by his extra judicial murder at the hands of the police. Since then through official bungling, negligence, complacency or collusion Boko Haram became a terrifying force taking tens of thousands of lives and capturing several towns and villages covering swathes of Nigerian sovereign territory."*

Illocutionary Act: This is an act of informing. Here the former president provides background knowledge of the formation, activities and reality of the terrorist sect. This indicates a sense of unacceptability, and a sense of determination to end the operations of the terrorist sect.

Misconstruation: More than 88% of the people consulted believe that the former president initially used the terrorist group to his own advantage at some point. Also, knowing the background information suggests that the former president may be or know the sponsors of this group. Thus a sense of distrust is created here, instead of determination to end the operations of the terrorist group in the country.

Perlocutionary Effect: This creates the effect of deceit and distrust.

(Excerpt from Bola Ahmed Tinubu Inaugural Speech)

Data 6.

Locution: "Our administration shall govern on your behalf but never rule over you. We shall consult and dialogue but never dictate."

Illocutionary Act: This is a commissive act of promising. Here the president is promising to rule the country based on the principles of democracy. The act of this statement is rhetorical. This is suggestive that the President persuasively intends to convince the people that their best bet is democratic governance.

Misconstruation: The statement from the president suggests that government shall be in the hands of powerful cabal with whom the president hopes to consult and dialogue.

Perlocutionary Effect: The effect of this is that the citizens should expect democracy in the form of oligarchy.

Data 7.

Locution: *"In this vein, may I offer a few comments regarding the election that brought us to this juncture. It was a hard fought contest. And it was also fairly won. Since the advent of the Fourth Republic, Nigeria has not held an election of better quality."*

Illocutionary Act: This is an act of informing. However the last sentence suggests that the president strongly assert that the credibility of the electoral process that brought him into power should never be doubted.

Misconstruation: The electoral process was marred with irregularities. Thus creating a sense of distrust in the government.

Perlocutionary Effect: This creates a sense of distrust in the electoral process and the government.

Data 8.

Locution: *"Rural incomes shall be secured by commodity exchange boards*

guaranteeing minimal prices for certain crops and animal products. A nationwide programme for storage and other facilities to reduce spoilage and waste will be undertaken. Through these actions, food shall be made more abundant yet less costly. Farmers shall earn more while the average Nigerian pays less."

Illocutionary Act: This is an act of assuring and promising that the agricultural sector of the economy shall be fully utilised to the interest of Nigerians. This is expected to inspire hope that there will be abundance of food, and at a cheaper price.

Misconstruation: This statement creates a sense of vocal noise, as there are no practical ways of attaining food security. Also, the audience is not able to distinguish how farmers will earn more if the citizens pay less.

Perlocutionary Effect: This is confusing, as there are no practical ways to ensure food security.

Data 9.

"We commend the decision of the outgoing administration in phasing out the petrol subsidy regime which has increasingly favoured the rich more than the poor. Subsidy can no longer justify its ever-increasing costs in the wake of drying resources. We shall instead re-channel the funds into better investment in public infrastructure, education, health care and jobs that will materially improve the lives of millions."
(Subsidy is Gone!)

Illocutionary Act: This is an act of commendation, and confirmation. Here the president confirms that the fuel subsidy policy cripples the economy in a way, and redirecting the funds into proper investment channels would be more profitable for Nigerians.

Misconstruation: The statement suggests a misdirection of leadership, as the removal of subsidy brought about untold hardships, disillusionment, and loss of confidence in the government.

Perlocutionary Act: This creates the effect of mixed feelings, and unknown future implications for the masses.

Data 10.

Locution: *"Whatever merits it had in concept, the currency swap was too harshly applied by the CBN given the number of unbanked Nigerians. The policy shall be reviewed. In the meantime, my administration will treat both currencies as legal tender."*

Illocutionary Act: The president performs an act of assertion. Here he asserts that the implementation of the currency swap policy was harsh, and that both currencies are recognised as legal tender. This is expected to create an effect of cheerfulness, as Nigerians can use both currencies as medium of exchange.

Misconstruation: A huge number of people in the country still holds that there is an "Old currency and a New currency," this is in contrast with President Tinubu's statement, in that he referred to both as legal tender.

Perlocutionary Effect: This creates an effect of uncertainty and anxiety.

DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

From the data presentation and analysis, there are instances of Misconstruation in speaker's intent and audience interpretation. This discrepancy is found in the Illocutionary act, perlocutionary Force. The responses from the survey of 200 people from different socio-cultural backgrounds suggest that Nigerians meticulously read to interpret the statements of their political leaders. This gives them a sense of direction on where to place their faith in the next four years. Thus, 88% of the responses received suggest that citizens Nigeria have high distrust in their political system and governance. However, there are some policy that may provide immediate succor such as the non-recognition of currency swap by the previous administration, Nigerians still believes that most of these policies is not only beneficial to the masses but it is especially more beneficial to the political leaders. This thereby creates a sense of Oligarchy instead of democratic governance.

In line with its aim and objectives, the findings of this study reveal that both President Tinubu and former President Buhari utilized a range of speech acts in their inaugural address. This study reveals that President Tinubu and Former President Buhari

employed a variety of speech acts in their speeches, such as promises, assurances, pledges, acknowledgments, appeals to unity, and declarations of commitment. These speech acts were used for different reasons, including building trust, instilling optimism, highlighting policy goals, and fostering national cohesion. However, it was observed that the Pragmatic Force on some of the statements met with misconstruction between speaker's intent and audience interpretation and actions. Based on the findings, the study recommends that political leaders especially those aspiring for the number one public office in the country should be cognisant of the power of speech acts and its pragmatic force on the public. Thus, studies like this will no doubt serve as an eye-opener and feedback analysis from their selected speechwriters. Thus, policy statements and directions should be stated overtly to avoid misconstruction by the public.

CONCLUSION

This study has cautiously revealed the ways in which presidents use language in their Speeches especially Inaugural speech to perform actions. This is especially true, if the speech has a preponderance of assertive acts. These assertions could be in the form of policy statements, thereby creating a sense of political readiness to tackle the challenges of the country. However, it was observed that the citizens are often more interested in the speech of their Presidents, in order to give them a clear sense of direction for the foreseeable future. This therefore implies that these Speeches are subjected to rigorous interpretation, and consequently further beneficial or detrimental actions. Thus, it is therefore necessary, that speechwriters overtly state their plans, with the masses in mind, and that Inaugural Speeches should help to inspire hope and confidence rather than disillusionment.

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